
An Exploratory Study of Digital Learning in Property Industries in Indonesia a Case of Jababeka and Sinarmas Land

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ABSTRACT: Using qualitative thematic analysis, researcher figure out learning drivers for using digital learning platform. The subject that tested divided into 3 generations that exists in PT. Jababeka Tbk and Sinar mas Land which are Generation X, Generation Y and generation Z. Each Generations has their respective points of view towards digital learning. Using motivation theory's elements, factors that played to drive these 3 generations in using digital learning. Researcher also found that nowadays, older generations (generation X) has not had difficulties in using Digital learning anymore as previous stigma in early pandemic era. The stigma where stating older generation has difficulties to keep up with digital transformation proven invalid in this writing. Their hindrance in using digital learning platform is only due to their physical ability such as old eye sight and blue light from gadget; not from the motivation of them or their resistance to change and adapt. In Motivation theory of self-actualization Maslow, employee is trying to self-actualize by acquiring new skills and knowledge. Herzberg also state that there are hygiene factor in a form of company SOP and rules that in fact urge employee with low learning appetite to use digital learning while motivation factor in Herzberg push people to achieve to be recognize and to get personal growth. Similar with Herzberg motivation theory, ERG by Alderfer's also strengthen the argument by need to grow. Lastly, McClelland theory in regards to need of affiliation also shown that older generation (gen X) has need to be keep up with current trend and don't want to be left behind.

KEYWORDS: digital learning, motivation theory; Generation X; Generation Y; Generation Z

LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital learning across 3 generational of Employees

Gen X is the era that observed their parents work fantastically difficult and long, frequently remaining steadfast to one company. This persuades Gen X to look for a healthy compromise, whereby work and way of life are adaptable and adjusted, fulfilling their money-related, family, and individual needs. They are the first generation to utilize computers in their homes and schools. Brought up in a period of innovative and social alter, they're tech-savvy and open to change. Generation Y (or later can be called as Gen Y) as a digitally competent and exceedingly connected era, Millennials utilize the web, mobile phones, social media, and YouTube to get to data rapidly and proficiently. Millennials favor technology-based learning from numerous, effectively open sources. They esteem solid individual associations and individualized encounters. Gen Z individuals are more down to earth and cautious than their Millennial partners. In common, people in this gather perused less and easier to accept new things. To connect with this era, utilize computerized infographics and brief, shareable recordings. Gen Z learners favor to be locked in in their learning, so interactive diversions and apps will offer assistance to fortify critical data. Instead of having a divider of flyers, a computerized library of infographics available by means of the quiet entrance is most successful.

Hertzberg Theory

Hertzberg classified the needs into two broad categories; namely hygiene factors and motivating factors. Hygiene issues, concurring to Herzberg, cannot motivate workers but can minimize disappointment, while Motivation is a force that pushes people to work with a high level of commitment and focus, even if things are going against them. The individual tends to seek recognition of others when they have accomplished something. Recognition from peers or superiors may affect the employees in achieving something. It may be better performance or urgency to upgrade skills and knowledge through various learning channels.

Alderfer's ERG Theory

In this model the letter E, R, & G each stand for a different human need: existence, relatedness, and growth. Alderfer's model says that all humans are motivated by these three needs. Existence needs concern our basic material requirements for living, which includewhat Maslow categorized as physiological needs such as air, sleep, food, water, clothing, sex and shelter and safety-related needs such as health, secure employment, and property. Relatedness needs got to do with the significance of keeping up interpersonal

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connections. These needs are based on social intelligent with others and are adjusted with Maslow's levels of love/belonging-related needs such as fellowship, family, and sexual closeness and esteem-related needs such as picking up the regard of others. While growth needs portray our natural crave for individual advancement.

McClelland's Theory of Motivation

McClelland's theory contrasts from Maslow's and Alderfer's, which center on satisfying existing needs instead of making or creating needs. This prevailing motivator depends on our culture and life experiences.

The three motivators are achievement, affiliation, power. According to Alex Acquahet al., (2021), the three-factor can be defined as follow:

Achievement is the requirement for accomplishment includes the crave to independently master objects, thoughts and other individuals, and to extend one's self-regard through the work out of one's ability.

Affiliation motivation – a need for love, having a place and relatedness, that's individuals have a solid require for companionships and need to have a place inside a social bunch, got to be preferred and held in well-known respect.

Authority/power motivation – a need to control over one's possess work or the work of others. These persons are authority motivated. There's a strong need to lead and to succeed in their thoughts. It is additionally required to extend individual status and distinction.

RESEARCH METHOD

Measurement

This research measures four motivational theories that will play a big role as learning drivers in using E-Learning. Starting from McClelland's theory, Alderfer's ERG, Mashlow, and Hertzberg theory. Research implemented using the thematic analysis method to study the relationship between variables.

Participants

In this research, the researcher uses the Qualitative method with mixed of FGD (Focus Group Discussion) and FI (Focus interview). There are 9 Respondents from *Sinarmas Land* and 8 respondents from Jababeka, creating a total of 17 Respondents. The interview was conducted for average 30 minutes per FGD session, And 15 minutes for FI Sessions. The interviews conducted online throughout December 2022.

Method

Thematic analysis is widely used by qualitative researchers, which is appropriate strategy of investigation for looking for to get it encounters, considerations, and behaviours over a information set. (Kiger and Varpio, 2020). Thematic analysis may be a powerful however flexible method for analysing qualitative information that can be used inside a variety of paradigmatic or epistemological orientations. Given the adaptability of thematic analysis, researchers utilizing this method must clearly layout their paradigmatic introductions and presumptions to guarantee the reliability of their discoveries and elucidations.

The thematic analysis could be a strategy for analysing subjective information that involves looking over information set to recognize, analysed, and report rehashed designs (Braun and Clarke, 2006). It could be a method for describing information, but it also involves translation within the forms of selecting codes and building topics. A recognized highlight of thematic analysis is its adaptability to be utilized inside a wide extent of hypothetical and epistemological systems and to be connected to a wide run of think-about questions, plans, and test sizes. As mentioned earlier, Thematic analysis is a fitting and effective strategy to utilize when looking for to get it a set of encounters, contemplations, or behaviours over information set. Since it is sketched out to explore for common or shared implications, it is less suited for looking at one-of-a-kind suggestions or experiences from a single person or information thing. There are 6 Steps in thematic analysis according to (Clarke and Braun, 2017), Familiarizing yourself with the data, Generating Initial Codes, Searching for Themes, Reviewing Themes, Defining and Naming Themes, and Producing the Report/Manuscript.

The researcher did data familiarizing by using the Qualitative method and Interviews as instruments, the researcher will analyses the recorded interview which consisting of 5 different answers per session from each respondent. Using a structured interview method, the FGI will be guided with questions that are infused with a motivation theory. The transcription of the Interview will be presented also in this writing, both FGI and Focus Interview. By analysing the point of view and opinion of the subject (3 generations of employees) towards its object (digital learning), the researcher will do a comparison study with the literature review that has been collected to find which factor will play the most in choosing digital learning.

The collected data will be classified based on the factors in motivation Theory. Then researcher will analyse the interview result by comparing them to the 4-motivation theory. In addition, the researcher also might compare the interview result to 16 learning drivers by Agrawal, R., et al (2021) to generate an understanding of Learning drivers. Through FGD Process the reliability and validity of one idea will be tested since participants or informants will point out their respective points of view and be tested by another participant.

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Relationship between Motivation theory to use E-learning in 3 generations

McClelland theory analysis

- Generation X is not having trouble to use digital learning platform
- Generation X does want to keep up with trends

In literature review, researcher found that Due to digital literacy Employees of certain ages such as generation X and late may perceive Digital learning as not user-friendly and troublesome. Based on research conducted by researcher to 6 People of generation X, there are no single statement from all 6 respondents that said Digital learning is troublesome or they are hindrance by digital literacy.

The generation X said that Digital learning is suitable for everyone, this also means regardless of what their ages is. Researcher also found that 3 generation X out of 6 respondents even already use Tik Toc, Instagram and YouTube as their learning platform. This phenomenon shows that Generation X has adapt to technology changes in post Covid era. This research also breaks the theory from (Irhandayaningsih, A. (2020), where he found that generation X and late may perceive Digital learning as not user-friendly and troublesome.

“Digital learning is usable everywhere, anytime and by Anyone” (Gen X- Jababeka’s Respondent)

“Right now, Tik Tok and Instagram is really simple, just 1 to 3 minutes per video. Time efficient and visual appealing.” (Gen X – Sinarmas Land)

However, The Generation X also agree that younger generation like Y and Z are easier to use digital learning due to their habits of using gadget since early childhood. The younger generation such as Gen Y and Z also agree with this statement. They think that generation Y and Z are more suitable to use Digital learning.

“The one that suitable in using E learning is Millennials or even the generation Z” (Generation Z from Sinarmas land)

“Actually the one that familiar with technology is the one that suitable to use Digital learning, if older generation are using it, I afraid it will not effective.”

(Generation Y from Sinarmas Land)

In this research, researcher has not found any objection from younger generation for Generation X to use Digital learning. They perceive Digital learning will not effective to Generation X but it does not mean that Digital learning is troublesome for older generation. Researcher think that generation X nowadays are having better adaptability towards technology development, including digital learning.

Psychological factor also known as an internal factor (Ramya, N. A. S. A. M., & Ali, S. M., 2016) affects consumer buying behaviour. The psychological factor includes four factors motivation, perception, learning, and memory (Qazzafi, S., 2020). According to Kotler, P. & Keller, K.L. (2016) environment will create perceptions that result in shaping the psychological factor. Pandemic situations and major restrictions created an ideal environment for digital learning to grow. This environment slowly pushes learner preference to choose ZOOM rather than blackboard (H Al Shammari, M., 2022). The researcher found, based on qualitative research, the situation plays a great factor as push factor for a person to become digital.

“At first in Covid Era, people left with no choice but online, from forced to be self-initiative to use digital learning.” (Generation Z – Sinarmas Land)

“The push factor is triggered by current situation where now we are entering Industrial 4.0 and 5.0, people are driven by technology. In Everyday life we are forced to shop using digital, buying token using digital, bank using digital, all is online and all of this trigger us to be techsavvy. So that we are forced to be used to with digital, including Learning.”

(Generation X – Jababeka)

Generation X also seems to be used to with using digital learning platform, leaving them with normal reaction and feeling towards using Digital learning. Based on Researcher’s experience, when pandemic hits for the first time, older generation felt proud to be able to use ZOOM as their meeting platform, however, after 3 years of pandemic, nowadays, researcher found that the feeling of using digital learning platform has lowered to basic needs, they treated digital learning as option similar as newer generation.

In Mc. Clelland theory there is one factor named need of affiliation or affiliation motivation. In here researcher found there are needs of affiliation from generation X to be able to keep up with younger generation. 2 Respondent from generation X said that:

“Does it sounds like younger generation Yet?” (Gen X – Sinarmas Land)

“We also want to know what is going on in nowadays situation” (Gen X – Sinarmas Land)

Here, the researcher draw conclusion that the needs for affiliation especially from older generation is one of the factor that drives them to use Digital learning.

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Self-actualization needs on Maslow's analysis

All generation react the same, their needs to self-actualize by using digital learning is coming from their self and not influenced by others.

Most of the respondents believe that their decision to use Digital learning is coming from internally, which is from the inside willingness of a person and not influenced by other conduct. The changes in the situation because of COVID will affect the situation that forces people to use Digital learning. This means that the factor that triggering people to use digital learning is not based on social interaction but people have been feeling the ease and simplicity of using digital learning. There generations react the same by saying Internal factor plays role in choosing whether to use Digital learning or Traditional onsite learning. The respondent made up their mind first to use Digital learning than starting to choose which platform is suitable to use.

"For me it's self-driven and not influenced by Others." (Gen Z - Jababeka)

"In my opinion, is self-driven, even there is influence from others, in the beginning is still our will to use digital learning. (Generation Z – Sinarmas land)

Maslow stated that, in order to reach the top of pyramids, one should complete the needs on the below pyramid, or otherwise the top of the pyramids will be disturbed. In this research, the researcher found that, generation X are having difficulties in completing their physical needs due to their body prowess and eye sight. In principle, researcher found that all 3 generations has a positive answer towards Digital learning. They welcome the advancement of technology in every aspect of their life, including in learning. Generation X perceived Digital learning as a new method of learning and a part of technology advancement. However, Since Generation X has older age compared to Y and Z, Generation X has limitations in stamina as well as eyesight in conducting the digital learning process. Generation X felt that using Digital learning is tiring for their eyes, looking up at the small screen on a mobile phone or brightness level on a laptop and computer becoming a hindrance for them to do Digital learning. In conclusion, the researcher found that the older generation is not handicapped by technology but more by age and is lightly resilient towards screens. Also, the font and small display on gadget becoming limitation for this older age.

"Font in the handphone is too small for people with older age." (Generation Y – Sinarmas Land)

"For me, the blue light in gadget is more tiring than a book" (Generation X – Sinarmas Land)

As for younger generation (Gen Y and Gen Z) seems having no problem for using digital learning. This is show to us that in order to be acceptable for all user, Digital learning that designed should not contain lots of words and more to the point rather than conventional. The platform that used for digital learning platform should think about how to accommodate the hindrance of older generation in terms of physical ability of them. In this case, Maslow are correct in determining the pyramid base by using physical needs. Generation X will not be able to completely self-actualize in using digital learning platform due to their body limitation.

Alderfer's ERG analysis

Personal Growth in ERG theory become driver for 3 generation to use Digital learning

The researcher found that Current technology has enabled digital learning platforms to be accessible even with low-end smart phone or computers. Most of them are also a web-based on, meaning that the device itself has no function of execution, and just as similar to opening Chrome for surfing on the Internet. So regardless of what type of the device is, whether is Expensive or not, digital learning has no issue at all. Also talking about financial status, most of the respondents also agree that Digital learning is way cheaper than offline learning. Since the model and module of digital learning is diverse, researcher also believe that, any kind of occupation will be beneficial by using digital learning. Even though Researcher also agree with respondent that said, practical and direct monitoring is necessary for a hard skill program such as basic lifesaving, forklift, etc, but by using digital learning, we can use blended method that will create effectiveness and efficiency. The researcher also agrees by respondents' ideas that digital learning can be paused and resumed, making it easier to review the material. These factors are facilitating the needs of personal growth across generational workforce.

All 3 generations are pursuing personal growth. From the research, the researcher found that they will feel happy after acquiring new skills. This finding validates ERG theory that state Growth is one of the factor from needs that push them to use digital learning. *I felt gain something when I did online learning, especially when I passed post-test. (Gen Z – Sinarmas land)*

"When accomplished something I felt satisfied." (Gen X – Sinarmas Land) "I want to know something new." (Gen Y – Jababeka)

Hertzberg theory analysis

Hygiene factor and motivating factors especially recognition and growth becoming push factor to use digital learning.

When talking about hygiene factor in this theory researcher found that learning obligation or mandatory learning program from company becoming push factor for person to use digital learning. Despite of the needs to learn and acquiring new skills, for some people, mandatory program is one of the reasons they use digital learning.

"But honestly, I use digital learning because of office regulation that mandatories to use digital learning."

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(Gen Y- Jababeka)

Some of respondent also believe that mandatory program is basically from the lack of competencies that found by companies which should be fulfilled by individuals.

“Mandatory means it’s our lack. It supposed to be not troublesome.” (Gen Y- Sinarmas Land) “Must is a must. As long as we can.” (Gen Y- Sinarmas Land)

In reality, researcher found that learning appetite of employee may differ from one to one. One group of employees with high learning appetite will do self-learning willingly. They will actively be seeking learning opportunities through various channels, including Digital platform. The other group with low appetite needs to be set by certain rules for them to accomplish certain modules on training. This low appetite group will work best with hygiene factors from Herzberg's theory, urge them to learn using various channels, including Digital learning.

The other factor in Herzberg's theory is Motivation theory. As mentioned in literature review, Achievement, Recognition and self-growth becoming learning drivers for employees to use Digital learning. Based on interview and discussion, researcher found that younger generations like Gen Y will seek achievement in acquiring new skills as well as certificates in addition to courses that they finished as proof of recognition. When recognition is applicable for their work they will feel growth.

“The E-certificate that can be used in workplace also motivating.” (Gen Y – Jababeka)

Implication and recommendation

From this research, we can infer that digital learning is friendly to use by all generations regardless of age and financial status. For a Digital learning platform developer, this is a good opportunity since the situation in psychological factors plays in nurturing a good ecosystem of digital. For corporations and Business firms, digital learning can be one of a good way of learning that provides time efficiency, budget efficiency, and more effective learning for employees. Since the accomplishment of the needed module is more affecting than the using of digital learning itself, Company should create or choose a digital learning platform that can accommodate many needs from every aspect (various modules available). In the eyes of businesses, digital learning can accommodate budget efficiency and higher time efficiency.

The researcher recommends a digital learning platform to provide a friendly user experience for older generations as they see capabilities and focus as not as good as newer generations. User experience and simplicity will become a point to note when developing and choosing the right digital learning platform and media, as they might vary from one perception to others.

Good digital learning is also the one that can create “the needs” or urgency to customers on why they need to enroll in certain courses. A variety selection of modules will be a key to the success of your digital learning. When the need of using a certain module in Digital has been created, people will be starting to use digital learning platforms.

Also, a good digital learning platform is one that can retain the interest of consumers to keep learning in a particular module or platform. Thus, the researcher recommends digital learning that has an interactive session in between courses as well as a good speaker of modules. Good digital learning is not boring but creates efficiency and effectiveness.

To increase learning engagement in using digital learning, based on motivation theory, a good system must provide:

- New Skills and knowledge
- Recognition that applied to work (can be certificate or point reward from company)
- Mandatory learning program
- Campaign on current update in a scope of learning.

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